

Active Constituents of *Vanda roxburghii* R. Br.

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Vanda roxburghii R. Br. is an epiphytic herb of the natural order Orchidaceae. An indigene of the hotter parts of India it is commonly known as 'Rasna' in Bengal and elsewhere. *V. roxburghii* is said to possess many of the important therapeutic properties, like the beneficial action on piles, rheumatism, sciatica and various other inflammatory and nervous diseases, moreover, the plant has been in extensive use both in the Hindu and Yunani medicines'.¹ Earlier workers² mentioned, during the pharmacological studies of the plant materials, the presence of a non-toxic glycoside (which stimulates all organs), a bitter principle, tannins, resin, saponin and sterols besides fatty oils and colouring matters. As the chemical studies of the plant has not been done so far, we took up the whole plant for its investigation, specially to isolate and characterize the bitter principle. The present studies reveal the presence of β -sitosterol, γ -sitosterol and two long chain fatty compounds in the whole plants.

PROCEDURE

The dried and powdered whole plant of *V. roxburghii* was extracted in a soxhlet apparatus with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol in succession for 48 hours. The petroleum extract, on removal of the solvent gave a semisolid substance which when chromatographed over Brockmann alumina gave a waxy material in the earlier fractions and a crystalline solid in the later fractions. The waxy material, A, on repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate and methanol mixture afforded light needles, m.p. 85°. The compound 'A' is soluble in benzene, chloroform, ether and petrol and gave a single spot on a TLC plate. The infrared spectrum of the compound in Nujol shows stronger bands at 3600, 2900, 2850, 1460, 1375, 1125, 1060, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . It is optically inactive, transparent in the ultraviolet and gives negative tetranitromethane test for unsaturation. The N.M.R. spectrum of the compound 'A' shows only one very strong and sharp proton peak at 1.25 δ and the nature of the spectrum is similar to that of a long chain fatty compound.

The crystalline solid, obtained in the later fractions of the chromatogram, showed positive Leibermann's test and gave a twin spot on thin layer chromatography over alumina containing about 10 percent of plaster of paris. This, on rechromatography, could be separated into two fractions. The earlier fractions on crystallisation from methanol gave a colourless crystalline substance, m.p. 148°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -44^\circ$ (CHCl₃). It readily formed

1. Chopra, Nayar and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 252.
2. Kirilukar and Basu, Indian Medicinal Plants, 1939, 4, 2406.
3. Gupta, Ray and Sengupta, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1946, 34, 253.

an acetate, m.p. 143°, [α]_D²⁰ -48° (CHCl₃). The substance was found identical with an authentic sample of γ -sitosterol. The later fractions of the chromatogram, on crystallisation from methanol gave another solid, m.p. 137°, [α]_D²⁰ -35° (CHCl₃), acetate, m.p. 128°, [α]_D²⁰ -39° (CHCl₃), and found to be identical with β -sitosterol.

The benzene extract of the plant material, on similar treatment of chromatography followed by crystallisation from benzene methanol mixture gave needles 'B', m.p. 88°. The compound is freely soluble in petrol, benzene, ether and chloroform but sparingly in methanol. Like 'A' the compound 'B' is also inactive and gives negative colour reaction with tetranitromethane. It is transparent in U.V. and its I.R. spectrum in Nujol shows bands at 3460, 2940, 2870, 1740, 1475, 1180, 730 and 725cm⁻¹. Its N.M.R. spectrum is practically of the same pattern as that of the compound 'A'. On TLC plate, it also showed a single spot. When admixed with 'A', the m.p. of 'B' lowered to 65° and the mixture showed twin spots on the TLC plate. All these properties indicate that like 'A', 'B' also belongs to straight chain fatty series. As the compounds 'A' and 'B' were obtained in small quantities and seems to have no phytochemical novelty, their further studies were discontinued.

The dark red methanolic extract on working up, following the usual procedure, gave a resinous mass which did neither give any positive test for alkaloid nor any bitter principle could be isolated from it.

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